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Socio-economic Problems Faced by Male Elderly Persons in Pashtun Society (A case study of Umarzai Charsadda)

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Abstract

Aging is a natural phenomenon. The increasing aging population is emerging challenge for both developing and under develop countries. Population ageing regarded as one of the most critical challenge of developed societies. Every phase of life has different problems. Pakistan older population, which has reached already 12.5 million, will double by 2030 and will reach to close 40 million by 2050. In pakhtun society, male elderly person respected recognized important part of the family. However, with time humans become weak lose their status become dependent socially and financially on family members in society. The the last phase of life arise different challenges to the aging population. There are so many challenges are exist in Pashtun society for older people. This research paper focused on socio-economic problems faced by male elderly in Pashtun society a study of Umarzai charsadda. It is quantitative in nature total sample size was 40 population above from age 60 male elderly people in Umarzai charsadda. Using non-probability convenience sampling data was collected with the help of structured interview questions. Data analyzed by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings revealed that the majority of male elderly persons were illiterate dependent on family unsatisfied with their current income, poverty ratio has high in Umarzai, on the other hand male elderly financially supporting their sons, most male elderly has two earning members in family, decrease mobility limited social participation in society, and poverty ratio is high. This research underscores the importance of older people are treasure for the young peoples and government and non-government organization highlight the issues of the elderly persons in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, resolve their pension issues.

Keywords: Aging, convenience sampling, Aging Population, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS),

Introduction

Aging is a natural and universal process, not solely determined by one's health but also influenced by various personal, social, and mental factors. This multidimensional phenomenon is an inherent part of the human life cycle, experienced by all individuals in society, across generations, tribes, and countries (sarwar & Tarannum, 2019). Different nation consider older persons with different digit use for older persons here, in Pakistan is that a person above 60 considered older. Countries often have different age categories, considering an older person, like 65 to 105 years or older (vector, 2004).

The socio-economic problems faced by older adults are multifaceted and deeply intertwined with various factors such as income, education, healthcare access, and social support. Research indicates that socio-economic status (SES) significantly influences the quality of life among older individuals. For instance, highlight that conventional measures of SES, particularly household income and education level, are crucial in identifying the risks of poor quality of life among older populations across Europe (Knesebeck et al., 2007). In Pakistan, elderly individuals face challenges such as poverty, neglect by family members, loneliness, and illness (Gulzar et al., 2008). These issues compounded by changing family structures, limited reemployment opportunities, and a lack of social policies addressing elderly needs (Alam et al., 2017).

These problems include social isolation, loneliness, cognitive decline, lack of interaction with the younger generation, guilt, sleeping disorder, not participating in political and religious activities, financial issues, family conflict, lack of decision-making, emotional problems, socio-economic problems, etc. This issue affects older individuals residing in Pakistan's urban and rural areas. In rural regions, older adults often settle in homes lack modern facilities and deprived of essential facilities compare to the urban areas.

Problem statement

In 21st-century senior's citizens in Pakistan especially in pakhtun, society struggle is their social economic due to low-income country. The elderly population faces different challenges depend on family, less satisfaction from the current income, large family structure, Government and non-government organization lack of focus in Pashtun society on aging population. Many things can cause health problems, which frequently neglected in favor of physical health issues. These include losing loved ones (spouses, for example) and jobs. (Khaki, 2023).

Humans become physically, mentally, economically, and socially weak with time. In Paktoon society, especially male elderly lose their status due to ageing, dependent on children's problems in many aspects of life—older people's issues are hidden in Pashtun society (Maira & Derbyshire, 2024). Pakistan's elderly population is estimate to be 7.2 million and is steadily increasing to about 10 per cent of the population (Trust, 2011). As of 2019, almost 15 million people in Pakistan are over 60, constituting 7% of the country's total population (Help Age Asia, 2020).

Research Objectives

1. To examine the demographic information of the older people.

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2. To highlight the male elderly economic issues in Umarzai charsadda.
3. To dig out the male elderly social issues in Umarzai.

Research Question

1. What are the socio-economic problems faced by male elderly persons in Pashtun society in Umarzai Charsadda.

Literature review

There are many problems faced in this period by older adults social include, including not having access to hospitals, loss of status, people's health, social isolation, aggressive orthodox behavior, and a decrease in memory. The study's authors found that most elderly individuals admitted to institutions came from nuclear households. In contrast to independent old individuals who do not reside in institutions, institutionalized elderly individuals are likely to encounter a range of social challenges, including mental health concerns. Researchers have also noted that elderly individuals living in institutionalized settings experience a more significant number of psychological issues compared to those who live outside of institutions. This is because non-institutionalized elderly individuals often encounter significant financial difficulties (Hemavathi1 & Rani, 2014).

Social problems are problems that face older people in society. These problems include lack of interaction in society, poverty, poverty, lack of participation in religious and political activities, and widowhood. The elderly population encounters many challenges, and one of the prominent issues they confront is inadequate housing. This predicament is prevalent among older individuals residing in both urban and rural areas. In rural regions, older adults often settle in homes lacking modern facilities, depriving them of essential facilities. Consequently, their living conditions are often substandard, characterized by scarcity and occasionally hazardous circumstances (Kourkota & Lambrini, 2016) In Pakistan, especially older adults, the population ratio is 11.3 million, which should increase to 43.3 million by 2050. According to a report by the United Nations, the percentage of older adults has increased from 8 percent in 1950 to 11 percent in 2007 and projected to reach 22 percent by 2050. The older adult population is growing at a rate of 2.6 percent. With the rapidly increasing older adult population, there is a need to improve the provision of elderly care in Pakistan. However, with the right strategies and interventions, we can create a more supportive and inclusive environment for the elderly, offering them a brighter and more hopeful future (Naurin et al., 2021).

Policies that ensure financial security, like affordable health care, pensions, and assistance, are crucial given the financial difficulties that many elderly people confront (Lu et al., 2023).

Those who have health insurance may not be fully protect from the costs associated with medical care. For medicines, tools, or services that are not covered by insurance, contributions, and out-of-pocket costs can mount up quickly. For many elderly people, this accumulation makes necessary care and treatments financially unaffordable (Zhou et al., 2022).

The study highlights the significance of offering older persons adequate social resources to enhance their quality of life. This includes specialized social services,

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tailored assistance, and a feeling of belonging to a community. Social workers can fulfill a vital function in overseeing family situations, creating programs, and overseeing social services. Policymakers should prioritize promoting age-friendly communities, education, income, social cohesion, solidarity, volunteerism, and lifelong learning, which satisfies older adults. Creating effective therapies that target psycho-social factors, such as accessible social resources, is crucial for maintaining overall well-being, limiting reliance on others, and reducing financial burdens (de leon, et al., 2020).

As individuals, enter old age, their mindset changes. One common fear faced by both rational and irrational elderly includes feelings of disregard, a decrease in responsibility, a decline in personal values, a sense of isolation, dementia, and a lack of family participation in society (kipgen & Sheikhohao, 2021).

Materials and method

The quantitative research method quantitative employed to explore the socio-economic problems faced by male elderly persons in Pashtun society in a study of Umarzai charsadda. We conducted structured interviews with open-ended questions for 15 to 25 minutes. Data collected from people who are above the age of 60 male elderly persons in the Umarzai one union council. Participants were select using convenience sampling for easily available. The data analysis was facilitated using quantitative analysis software SPSS, which help, organize, code and analyze the participants data with cross table and simple tables in SPSS.

Data analysis Results

Table 1: Age of the respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
60-65	18	45.0
66-75	11	27.5
76-85	10	25.0
86-90	01	2.5
Total	40	100

Description

The above table shows the age distribution of the respondents. Out of 40 respondents, 18 (45%) are aged 66-75, 11 (27%) are aged 76-85, 10 (25%) are aged 86-90, and 1 (2.5%) is aged above 90.

Findings:

The table shows that most of the respondents are of age 60-65.

Table 2: Marital status of respondents and their Current Status of Living.

Marital status of the respondent	Currently with living				Total
	Children	Grandchildren	Relative	Alone	
Single	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	2 66.7%	1 33.3%	3 7.5%
Married	27 93.1%	1 3.4%	0 0.0%	1 3.4%	29 100.0%
widowed	7 87.5%	1 12.5%	0 0.0%	0 0.0%	8 20.0%
Total	34 85.0%	2 5.0%	2 5.0%	2 5.0%	40 100.0%

Description

The table shows the older adults' marital status and living status. Out of 40, 3 respondents (7.5%) are single, 29 respondents (72.5%) are married, and 8 (20%) are widowed.

Out of 40, 34 (85%) older adults live with children. Next, 2 (5%) older people live with grandchildren. Additionally, 2 (5%) older adults live with relatives. Lastly, 2 (5%) older people live alone at home.

Findings

The table showed that 27 (93.1%) of 40 respondents are married. Of older adults, 34 (85%) live with children.

Table 3: Education of the Respondents

Education of the Respondents	Frequency	Per cent
Illiterate	24	60.0
Primary level	06	15.0
Middle	06	15.0

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Secondary	04	10.0
Total	40	100.0

Description

The above table shows the educational status of the respondents. Out of 40, 24 (60%) were illiterate. On the other hand, 6 (15%) revealed that they had primary-level education, 40 (15%) said that they had middle-level education, and the remaining 4 (10%) respondents had secondary-level education.

Finding:

The table shows that most of the respondent's majority of the respondents were illiterate.

Table No 4: Employment type of the respondents

Employment type	Frequency	Percent
Agriculture	8	20.0
Business	12	30.0
skilled labor	13	32.5
Unskilled labor	7	17.5
Total	40	100.0

Description:

The above table shows the current employment type of older people in Umarzai. The analysis shows that out of 40, 8 (20.0%) are agriculture workers in their fields. Secondly, out of 40, 12 (30%) are doing business; some have a shop selling food. Thirdly, out of 40, 13 (32.5%) are skilled laborers; fourthly, 40, 7 (17.5%) are unskilled laborers.

Finding:

The table shows that most of the respondents out of 40, 13 (32.5%) respondents are skilled labor.

Table No 5: Number of children and the type of family of respondents

Number of Children of the male elderly	Family type of the respondent			Total
	Joint	Nuclear	Extended	
0	1 50.0%	0 .0%	1 50.0%	2 5.0%
4	4 100.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	4 100.0%
5	7 70.0%	2 20.0%	1 10.0%	10 25.0%
7	6	0	1	7

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7	85.7%	.0%	14.3%	17.5%
8	8 50.0%	5 31.2%	3 18.8%	16 40.0%
5	1 100.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	1 2.5%
Total	27 67.5%	7 17.5%	6 15.0%	40 100.0%

Description

The table shows the respondents' number of children. Out of 40, 2 (5.0%) respondents have 0 children. Out of 40, 4 (10%) respondents have four children. Next, out of 40, 10 have five children (25%). Out of 40, 17.5% have seven children. Furthermore, out of 40, 8 (40%) have children. Additionally, out of 40, 1 (2.5%) respondent has five children.

On the other hand, out of 40, 27 (67.5%) of the older respondents belong to the joint family. Secondly, out of 40, 7 (17.5%) respondents belonged to the nuclear family system, out of 100%. Additionally, out of 40, 6 (15.0%) belong to the extended family system,

Findings:

The table shows that 16 of the 40 respondents have eight children (40%). Of the 40, 27 older people belong to the joint family, 67.5% out of 100%.

Table 6: status of Retirement of the respondents and their pension

Are you retired from a government organization	Amount Pension				Total
	12000	20000	30000	0	
Yes	4 50.0%	2 25.0%	2 25.0%	0 .0%	8 20.0%
No	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	32 100.0%	32 80.0%
Total	4 10.0%	2 5.0%	2 5.0%	32 80.0%	40 100.0%

Description

The above table shows retired older persons. The data shows that out of 40, 8 (20.0%) older adults are retired from government and semi-government

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institutions. While out of 40, 32 (80.0%) are not retired from government organizations. Next, how much is the pension of the older people here? The analysis shows that out of 40, 4 (10.0%) have a 12,000 Pakistani rupee pension. Furthermore, 40, 2 (5.0%) have 20000 rupees. Additionally, out of 40, 2 (5%) have a 30,000 Pakistani rupee pension. Lastly, out of 40, 32 (80.0%) have not received a pension.

Findings:

The table shows that 32 out of 40 (80.0%) respondents are not retired from government organizations. The analysis shows that 4 out of 40, 10.0%, have a 12,000 Pakistani rupee pension.

Table No 7: Whom is currently earning members in the family and the how many number of earning members in the respondents' families.

Whom Currently, earning member in family	Number Of Earning Members				Total
	1	2	3	4	
Son	2 6.1%	14 42.4%	6 18.2%	11 33.3%	33 82.5%
Self-employed	0 0%	1 14.3%	4 57.1%	2 28.6%	7 17.5%
Total	2 5.0%	15 37.5%	10 25.0%	13 32.5%	40 100.0%

Description

The above cross table shows who an earning member is and how many earning members are in the family. Here, 33 out of 40 are (82.5%). While older adults are self-employed and work as security guards, some work in the shops. 7 out of 40 being (17.5%). The following 15 out of 40 older adults, 37.5%, have two families in their family. 13 out of 40 (32.5%) of 100% are earning members, while 2 out of 40 are (5.0%) of 1 member. Lastly, 10 out of 40, or 25.0%) of 100 have three members earning in the family.

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Findings:

The table showed that most of the respondents, 33 out of 40 (82.5%), are supporting older people and their sons, while 15 older adults (37.5%) have two earning families in their family.

Table No 8: Source of income and satisfaction from the income of the respondents

Source of income of the respondents.	Satisfaction from income		Total
	Yes	No	
Land	6 75.0%	2 25.0%	8 20.0%
Employment	4 40.0%	6 60.0%	10 25.0%
Family Support	7 53.8%	6 46.2%	13 32.5%
Pension	2 22.2%	7 77.8%	9 22.5%
Total	19 47.5%	21 52.5%	40 100.0%

Description

The above table showed the respondent's income source and their satisfaction with the income. The result shows that 8 out of 40 is 20.0% of the source of income, while 10 out of 40 is (25%) of employment. The following 13 out of 40 (32.5%) depend on their family. 9 out of 40, which is 22.5%, have a pension as their source of income.

Additionally, 19 out of 40 respondents (47.5%) are satisfied with their income, while 21 out of 40 (52.5%) are dissatisfied.

Findings:

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The table shows that most respondents are 40, with 13 (32.5%) depending on their family. Of 40, 21 (52.5%) respondents are unsatisfied with their income.

Table No 9: Whom male elderly currently supporting financially and showing ownership of the home

Currently financially supporting of male elderly.	Ownership Of Home		Total
	Personal	Rented	
Son	20 69.0%	9 31.0%	29 72.5%
Grandchildren's	2 66.7%	1 33.3%	3 7.5%
Relatives	0 .0%	1 100.0%	1 2.5%
Noone	7 100.0%	0 .0%	7 17.5%
Total	29 72.5%	11 27.5%	40 100.0%

Description

The above table shows the ownership and rent of a home. Of the male elderly, out of 40, 29 have a personal home, while out of 40, 11 (27.5%) live in rental homes. On the other hand, financially, male elderly support out of 40, 29 (72.5%) are living with sons. Out of 40, 3 (7.5%) support their grandchildren financially. Out of 40, 1 (2.5%) supports their relative. Lastly, out of 40, 7 (17.5%) are not financially supported; some of them work in homes and sell food.

Finding:

The table shows that most of the respondents—40, 29 (72.5%)—are male elderly financially their sons. On the other, hand out of 40, 29 being 72.5% /100% have a personal home.

Table 10: Showing eating food together and interacting with younger people

Eating together family	food with	Interaction with younger Peoples			Total
		Daily	weekly	monthly	
	Yes	26 96.3%	1 3.7%	0 .0%	27 67.5%
	No	10 76.9%	2 15.4%	1 7.7%	13 32.5%
Total		36 90.0%	3 7.5%	1 2.5%	40 100.0%

Description

People eating food together with their families shows the daily interaction between young people and older people in Pakistani society. The data analysis shows that out of 40, 27 (67.5%) are eating food together with their families, while out of 40, 13 (32.5%) are not eating food together with their families. Next interaction with family of younger with older people’s daily out of 40, 36 (90.0%). Out of 40, 3 (7.5%) interact weekly with their younger generation. Lastly, out of 40, 1 (2.5%) monthly interact with their younger generation.

Findings:

The table shows that most of the respondents, 27 out of 40, eat food together with their family, while 36 (90.0%) interact daily with their Family.

Table 11: currently who is earning members in the family and the number of earning members in the respondents' families?

Currently, who is earning member in family	Number Of Earning Members in the family				Total
	1	2	3	4	
Son	2 6.1%	14 42.4%	6 18.2%	11 33.3%	33 82.5%
Self-employed	0 0%	1 14.3%	4 57.1%	2 28.6%	7 17.5%
Total	2 5.0%	15 37.5%	10 25.0%	13 32.5%	40 100.0%

Description

The above cross table shows who an earning member is and how many earning members are in the family. Here, 33 out of 40 are (82.5%). While older adults are self-employed and work as security guards, some work in the shops. 7 out of 40 being (17.5%). The following 15 out of 40 older adults, 37.5%, have two families in their family. 13 out of 40 (32.5%) of 100% are earning members, while 2 out of 40 are (5.0%) of 1 member. Lastly, 10 out of 40, or 25.0%) of 100 have three members earning in the family.

Findings:

The table showed that most of the respondents, 33 out of 40 (82.5%), are supporting older people and their sons, while 15 older adults (37.5%) have two earning families in their family.

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Table No 12: Attending family functions and the reason for not participating in family functions.

Attending family function	Reason for not attending family functions				Total
	Not Applicable	Health reason	Not invited	Lack of interest	
Yes	3 100.0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	0 .0%	3 7.5%
No	0 .0%	24 64.9%	3 8.1%	10 27.0%	37 92.5%

Description

The above table shows the participation of older adults in family gatherings and the reasons for not attending family functions. The table shows that out of 40, 3 attending family functions (7.5%) out of 100%. Next, Out of 40, 37 (92.5%) are not attending family functions for several reasons. Furthermore, Out of 40, 24 (64.9%) older adults suffer from health illnesses. Additionally, 40, 3 (7.5%) out of 100% of respondents are not invited to family gatherings. Additionally, 40, 10, and 25.0% of 100 need more interest in family gatherings.

Findings:

The table shows that most of the respondents, 40, 26 (37%) out of 100%, do not attend family functions, while 24 (60.0%) do not attend family functions due to health problems.

Table No 13: Feeling of connection with the community of the respondents.

Responses	Frequency	Per cent
Yes	22	55.0
No	18	45.0

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Total	40	100.0
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The above tables show the connection older people have with the community. Here, the analysis shows that out of 40, 22 (55.0%) feel connected with the community, while out of 40, 18 (45%) do not. Some elderly have health issues. They are not able to communicate with their community.

Finding

The table showed that most respondents, 40 22 (55.0%), feel connected to the community.

Results and Discussion

This is a present study about the “socio-economic problems faced by male elderly in Pashtun Society: A study of Umarzai Charsadda. The study, conducted in Umarzai, covered one union council and intended to discover the socio-economic problems male older adults face in Umarzai Charsadda KPK. The elderly population is an essential unit of all societies. With time, humans become weak physically, socially, and economically. Due to ageing, their status changes at the family and social levels.

This study focused on the socio-economic problems, facing male elderly persons in Umarzai. The data collected from the above-age 60 male elderly; most respondents were between 60 and 65. The total sample size was 40, using a non-probability, convenience sampling data collection tool and a structured interview. Lastly, I used SPSS software to analyze the results.

Most of the respondents were age, i.e., 60-65 (see table 1), Most respondents, i.e., 40, 27 (93.1%), are married, (see table 2) and Most were illiterate (see table 3). The table shows that most of the respondents out of 40, 13 (32.5%) respondents are skilled labour (see Table 4). Most respondents, i.e., have eight children and belong to the joint family system (see Table 4). The table shows that 16 of the 40 respondents have eight children (40%). Of the 40, 27 older people belong to the joint family, 65.5% out of 100% (see table 5). Most respondents, i.e., 40, 32 (80.0%), are not retired from government organizations. Meanwhile, 8 /of 40 retired male elderly persons 4 have a 12,000-monthly pension, 2 elders have 20000, and another 2 elders have 40000 Pakistani rupee pension monthly (see table 6). The table showed that most of the respondents, 33 out of 40 (82.5%), are supporting older people and their sons, while 15 older adults (37.5%) have two earning families in their family (See Table 7). The table shows that most respondents are 40, with 13 (32.5%) depending on their family. Of 40, 21 (52.5%) respondents are unsatisfied with their income (see table 8). The table shows that most of the respondents—40, 29 (72.5%)—are male elderly financially their sons. On the other hand, out of 40, 29 72.5% /100% have a personal home (See table 9). The table shows that most of the respondents, 27 out of 40, eat food together with their family, while 36 (90.0%) interact daily with their Family (See Table 10). The table showed that most of the respondents, 33 out of 40 (82.5%), support older people with their sons, while 15 older adults (37.5%) have two earning families in their family (See Table 11). The table shows that most of the

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respondents, 40, 26 (37%) out of 100%, do not attend family functions, while 24 (60.0%) do not attend family functions due to health problems (See Table 12). The table showed that most respondents, 40 22 (55.0%), feel connected to the community (See Table 13).

Suggestions

1. Government and non-government institutions take the positive initiative to resolve the pension issue of the ageing population.
2. There need to be awareness among society about the senior citizens act 2014 Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan, must be implement practically in the real world.
3. To create separate parks in the cities for older adults.
4. Due to modernization, we lost the Hujra system and need to have community centres where elderly same-age people share ideas for minimizing social isolation.
5. Youngster should share ideas with the elderly peoples because of the high experience.
6. In finding the majority of male elderly suffering from the health disease every month checkups of male elderly, ensure the young generation.
7. Government and non-government organizations should facilitate to create businesses so that elderly people can run their businesses easily.
8. The ageing population is vulnerable in Pakhtoon society its responsibility of the all people to respect their elders.
9. Eliminating all forms of discrimination and providing an environment in which older people are protected from violence and abuse will help them exercise their choices and contribute to society.
10. The government launch a compliant cell for older adults to submit their complaints.

Conclusion

The study focused on the socio-economic problems faced by male elderly persons in Pashtun society. It concluded that with the structured interviews, the social and economic problems are identified in the results. Gender, education, marital status, family structure, income of the family, personal working of the respondents, social participation of the respondents, and satisfaction from income, investigated in the research. Low levels of education and illiteracy are associated with low productivity and unemployment, which increase chances of illnesses disability and death among older people so therefore, need to encourage continuous training in life and opportunities in the community to train older people with the new modernization era. . Retired individual less in male elderly multiple health issues due to lack of nursing homes concepts in Pakistan. It is therefore imperative that the country respond urgently to the most critical needs of its older people and at the same time promote more profound societal changes, which create an age-friendly and enabling environment in which people of all ages can flourish. Findings show most of the male elderly are not satisfied with their income supporting their sons there is no single daughter who supports the father due to a lack of education and skills. The majority of male elderly suffer from health illnesses government and non-government organizations

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should ensure that health services are aligned to the health needs of the older population, especially the primary health care level is essential to assist older people to remain active in their communities.

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